

Explainable diagnosis of transformer faults in the Ivorian network by DGA: interpretable LightGBM approach and inter-site transfer

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Abstract :

The integrity of electrical network transformers is crucial to the reliability and continuity of power supply in Côte d'Ivoire. Dissolved gas analysis (DGA), although widely used, faces interpretation limitations in tropical local contexts and in the face of diverse fault profiles. This article proposes an explainable diagnostic approach based on LightGBM, a high-performance gradient boosting algorithm, coupled with SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), an interpretability tool. The model is trained on DGA data from transformers in the Ivorian fleet, using both raw variables (concentrations of H₂, CH₄, C₂H₂, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, CO, CO₂) and derived variables (ratios normalized according to IEC 60599:2022). Performance is compared to traditional methods (Duval's triangle, IEC 60599:2022 normative approach, Rogers' normative methods), as well as other AI models (XGBoost, SVM). The explainability provided by SHAP makes it possible to identify the most discriminating gases or ratios, establish interpretable thresholds for maintenance, and visualize local explanations, thereby facilitating decision-making in the field. In addition, the study assesses inter-site transferability by training the model on data from Abidjan South and testing it on other regions of the network. The results demonstrate a notable improvement in diagnostic accuracy, gains in transparency, and satisfactory robustness in the context of transfer, paving the way for an operational dashboard for proactive monitoring of the Ivorian transformer fleet.

Keywords : Electrical transformers, Dissolved gases (DGA), LightGBM, SHAP, DGA ratios, Fault diagnosis, Predictive maintenance.

1. Introduction

Power transformers are a strategic link in the electricity grid, and their reliability directly affects service continuity and power supply stability [1],[2]. In Côte d'Ivoire, growing energy demand, driven by rapid urbanization and sustained industrial development, is forcing operators such as CI-ENERGIES and CIE (Compagnie Ivoirienne d'Electricité) to step up monitoring of this critical equipment [3],[4]. Unexpected failures not only lead to costly outages, but also pose risks of irreversible damage to assets and have consequences for the overall security of the network [5],[6].

Among conditional monitoring methods, dissolved gas analysis (DGA) has played a central role for several decades [7],[8]. This technique is based on the detection and quantification of gases produced by the decomposition of insulating paper and mineral oil in the presence of electrical or thermal faults [9]. Characteristic gases, such as H₂, CH₄, C₂H₂, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, CO and CO₂, can be used to identify the nature of the faults, whether they are partial discharges, localised heating or electric arcs [10],[11]. Historically, the interpretation of GD has been based on normative or semi-empirical approaches. Duval's triangle uses the relative concentration ratios of three hydrocarbons to classify faults [12], the IEC 60599 standard, revised in 2022, defines concentration thresholds and ratios to guide diagnosis [13], while Rogers' method is based on four gas ratios associated with a system of logical rules [14].

Although robust and easy to implement, these approaches have limitations in specific contexts [15]. Regional variability in fault profiles, influenced by tropical climatic conditions, insulating oil quality and maintenance history, can affect the relevance of diagnoses [16]. Furthermore, class overlap, resulting from the fact that different faults produce similar ratios, creates uncertainty and can lead to ambiguous diagnoses [17]. Finally, the lack of quantitative explainability makes it impossible to assess the relative importance of variables in the decision, which limits their value in an explainable and reproducible analysis framework [18].

With the rise of monitoring data and the rapid development of artificial intelligence, new data-driven approaches have emerged to improve diagnostic accuracy [19]. Among these, the Light Gradient Boosting Machine

(LightGBM) algorithm has established itself as a method particularly suited to the processing of tabular data, thanks to its speed of execution, its efficient management of missing data and its robustness in the face of unbalanced classes [20]. However, despite its performance, the transparency of machine learning models remains a major obstacle to their adoption in industry [21]. In this regard, SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) provide a relevant solution by quantifying the contribution of each variable, whether a gas or a ratio, to a given prediction [22]. This approach not only justifies the diagnosis to engineers, but also derives interpretable thresholds aligned with the IEC 60599:2022 standard.

This paper proposes the development of a LightGBM model for classifying transformer faults based on data from the DGA on the Ivorian electricity network. The originality of this study lies in the integration of SHAP to ensure the global and local explainability of the model, but also in the comparison with classical methods such as Duval's triangle, the IEC 60599 standard and Rogers' method, as well as with other artificial intelligence approaches such as XGBoost and SVM. Particular attention is paid to inter-site transferability, i.e. the ability of a model trained on a set of transformers in one area, notably Abidjan South, to be generalized and reliably applied to other areas of the network.

This research has two objectives: firstly, to improve diagnostic accuracy in order to detect critical faults more reliably, and secondly, to provide maintenance teams with an interpretable decision-making tool that is adapted to the realities of the Ivorian network and complies with the robustness and transparency requirements expected in a strategic industrial context.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data used

The data comes from Dissolved Gas Analysis (DGA) measurement campaigns carried out between 2018 and 2024 on a set of transformers in the Ivorian network operated by CI-ENERGIES and CIE (Compagnie Ivoirienne d'Electricité). Sampling covers several sites, including the Abidjan South area, but also other locations (Abidjan North, Bouaké, Yamoussoukro, for example) in order to assess the transferability of the model.

Each record corresponds to an oil sample analyzed by gas chromatography, in accordance with procedures compliant with IEC 60567 for sampling and IEC 60599:2022 for normative interpretation.

Table 1 gives the names and formulas of the various main gases in transformer oil and quantifies them (in ppm)::

Table 1: The various gases dissolved in transformer oil (DGA)

Name of gas	Hydrogen	Methane	Acetylene	Ethylene	Ethane	Carbon monoxide	Carbon dioxide
Formula	H_2	CH_4	C_2H_2	C_2H_4	C_2H_6	CO	CO_2

Metadata is associated with each measurement: date, location, transformer rated power, and diagnosed condition (when field confirmation is available). Table 2 provides an example of dissolved gas concentrations in the oil of ten (10) transformers in the Ivorian electricity network, most of which are located in southern Abidjan.

Table 2: Concentrations of dissolved gases in transformer oil in the Ivorian network [4]

[CO ₂]	[CO]	[H ₂]	[CH ₄]	[C ₂ H ₆]	[C ₂ H ₄]	[C ₂ H ₂]	[C ₃ H ₈]
1217	233,8	35,6	16,1	2	2	0,3	1,9
2211	104,5	6,7	2,2	1	0,9	< 0,1	1,4
4819	528,1	133,9	24,8	30,8	181,8	321,7	23,1
6523	528,2	72,8	15,1	7	5,5	0,2	6,1
1874	391,3	7,4	51,1	115,8	7,4	< 0,1	97,2
45049	508,9	91,2	159,5	203,2	100,3	5,4	164,5
4235	444,8	12,7	15,9	3,8	9,9	0,3	1,9

2717	328,1	97,8	20,2	30,1	22,5	4,4	28
4276	295	8,3	3,4	1,5	2,6	0,4	1,1
1345	404,2	13,7	10,6	9,4	0,9	< 0,1	7,7

2.2. Data pre-processing

Data pre-processing was carried out in three main stages. First, duplicate records and incomplete measurements were deleted to ensure data quality. Concentrations expressed as ‘< 0.1 ppm’ were replaced with a substitute value of 0.05 ppm to avoid introducing artificial zero values that could skew the statistical analyses. Next, outliers were detected using the interquartile range (IQR) method. The IQR is defined by equation (1):

$$IQR = Q_3 - Q_1 \tag{1}$$

Where Q1 and Q3 represent the first and third quartiles of the distribution, respectively. The outlier detection limits are given by equations (2) and (3):

$$B_{inf} = Q_1 - 1,5.IQR \tag{2}$$

$$B_{sup} = Q_3 + 1,5.IQR \tag{3}$$

Any value x satisfying $x < B_{inf}$ or $x > B_{sup}$ is considered potentially anomalous. These values were validated by experts in the field; observations confirmed as physically plausible were retained, while others were adjusted or removed from the analysis set. In addition to the raw values, gas ratios recommended by IEC 60599 and Rogers were calculated:

$$R_1 = \frac{CH_4}{H_2}, R_2 = \frac{C_2H_2}{C_2H_4}, R_3 = \frac{C_2H_2}{CH_4}, R_4 = \frac{C_2H_4}{C_2H_6}$$

These ratios are used in normative interpretation and can be integrated as features for the LightGBM model. The data were normalised using a logarithmic transformation to reduce the disproportionate influence of very high concentrations and improve the symmetry of the distributions. This transformation is expressed by equation (4):

$$x' = \log(x + 1) \tag{4}$$

Where x represents the raw value and x' the transformed value. Adding 1 avoids problems associated with zero values. In addition, the target classes were encoded into seven distinct categories, corresponding to the main types of defects identified, as shown in Table 3:

Table 3: Overview of the various faults and their codes

Code	Full name	Brief description
PD	Partial discharges	Local ionization in oil or solid insulation, without complete breakdown.
T1	Low warm-up	Temperature < 300 °C, often due to low local losses.
T2	Moderate warm-up	Temperature between 300 °C and 700 °C, linked to more pronounced heating of a component.
T3	High heat	Temperature > 700 °C, indicating intense heating that could damage the conductors.
D1	Low-energy discharges	Low-intensity localized dielectric breakdown.
D2	High-energy discharges	Intense dielectric breakdown, with risk of significant damage.
Normal	Normal operation	No defects detected in the measurements.

2.3. Modelling with LightGBM

The Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) algorithm was chosen because of its ability to efficiently process tabular, heterogeneous, and potentially unbalanced data, while offering an optimal compromise between performance and speed of execution [24].

LightGBM is based on the principle of Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT), where a set of weak models (decision trees) is trained sequentially to minimize a loss function \mathcal{L} . At each iteration t , a new tree $f_t(x)$ is learned on the residuals of the previous model, following relation (5):

$$F_t(x) = F_{t-1}(x) + \eta \cdot f_t(x) \tag{5}$$

Where η is the learning rate.

The direction of optimization is given by the negative gradient (equation 6) of the loss function:

$$g_i^{(t)} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(y_i, F_{t-1}(x_i))}{\partial F_{t-1}(x_i)} \tag{6}$$

LightGBM introduces two major optimizations that can be defined as Growth by Leaf-wise Splitting, where divisions are made by choosing the leaf that maximizes information gain, reducing the depth required to achieve high predictive power, and Histogram-based Binning, in which continuous values are grouped into intervals, reducing the complexity of finding the optimal split. In addition, LightGBM naturally handles class imbalances by adjusting instance weights, weighting each sample ω_i (Equation 7) proportionally to its importance in the minority class:

$$\omega_i = \frac{1}{n_{C(i)}} \tag{7}$$

Where $n_{C(i)}$ is the number of samples in class $c(i)$ of observation i .

LightGBM is an efficient variant of Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT). The model learns a predictive function $F(x)$ by adding new trees h_m to minimise a loss function \mathcal{L} . We have relations (8), (9) and (10).

$$F_0(x) = \underset{Y}{\text{arg min}} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{L}(y_i, Y) \tag{8}$$

$$g_{im} = \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(y_i, F_{m-1}(x_i))}{\partial F_{m-1}(x_i)} \right] \tag{9}$$

$$h_{im} = \left[\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{L}(y_i, F_{m-1}(x_i))}{\partial F_{m-1}(x_i)^2} \right] \tag{10}$$

The algorithm constructs a tree $h_m(x)$ to approximate $-\frac{g_{im}}{h_{im}}$ and then updates the function:

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \eta h_m(x) \tag{11}$$

Where η is the learning rate

Furthermore, the model's hyperparameters were optimized using exhaustive search (Grid Search) coupled with five-fold stratified cross-validation ($k=5$). The ranges of values tested are shown in Table 4:

Table 4: Tested value ranges

Num leaves	Max depth	Learning rate	Feature fraction	Bagging fraction	Min data in leaf
31 à 63	5 à 10	0,01 à 0,1	0,7 à 0,9	0,7 à 0,9	20 à 50

The optimisation criterion used is the macro-average F1 score, defined by equation (12):

$$F1_{macro} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i=1}^C \frac{2 \cdot Pr_i \cdot R_i}{Pr_i + R_i} \tag{12}$$

Where C is the total number of classes, Pr_i is the precision, and R_i is the recall of class i . This metric was chosen in order to give equal weight to each class, thereby limiting the bias induced by majority classes.

2.4. Interpretability with SHAP

2.4.1. Overall analysis

The overall interpretability of the model was obtained by calculating the average absolute importance of the SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values for each input variable. For a variable j , this importance is defined by equation (13).

$$Importance(j) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\phi_{i,j}| \quad (13)$$

Where $\phi_{i,j}$ represents the SHAP value associated with variable j for observation i , and N represents the total number of observations.

The results are visualized using a beeswarm plot, which allows us to assess the influence of high or low values of each gas on the prediction. The horizontal position reflects the impact on the model, while the color encodes the intensity of the variable.

2.4.2. Local analysis

For individual-level explanation, SHAP values are assigned to each prediction in order to decompose the model output in the form (equation 14):

$$f(x_i) = \phi_0 + \sum_{j=1}^M \phi_{i,j} \quad (14)$$

Where $f(x_i)$ is the prediction for observation i , ϕ_0 corresponds to the base value (average prediction) and M is the total number of variables.

Waterfall plots are generated to visually illustrate the positive or negative contribution of each variable to the prediction of a given sample. For example, for a confirmed D2 defect, the graph highlights the gases that contribute most strongly to the classification in this category. SHAP values are based on Shapley values in cooperative game theory. For an instance x , the contribution of variable j to the prediction is given by equation (15):

$$\phi_j = \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{j\}} \frac{|S|!(M-|S|-1)!}{M!} [f_{S \cup \{j\}}(x_{S \cup \{j\}}) - f_S(x_S)] \quad (15)$$

Where:

M = total number of variables,

S = subset of variables excluding j ,

f_S = model prediction using only the variables in S .

2.5. DGA ratios (IEC 60599)

Les ratios les plus utilisés pour caractériser les défauts selon l'IEC 60599 sont :

Les ratios DGA normalisés sont calculés selon IEC 60599 :2022 pour rendre les concentrations comparables et réduire la dépendance aux conditions locales :

$$R_1 = \frac{C_2H_2}{C_2H_4}, R_2 = \frac{CH_4}{H_2}, R_3 = \frac{C_2H_4}{C_2H_6}$$

Ces ratios sont ensuite comparés à des seuils normatifs pour assigner une classe de défaut (*Thermal, Discharge, PD*).

Ces ratios servent de variables explicatives dans le modèle LightGBM et sont essentiels pour l'interprétation via SHAP.

2.6. Méthodes de comparaison

To evaluate the relevance of the LightGBM + SHAP model, performance is compared to standard methods such as IEC 60599:2022, Duval's Triangle, Rogers, and alternative AI models that are equally effective, namely XGBoost, Random Forest, and SVM (One-vs-Rest). Each method is evaluated using the same training and test data sets.

2.7. Inter-site transfer methodology

The transferability of the model was assessed in a case study involving training the classifier on data from the Abidjan South site, then testing its performance on independent data collected from other sites in the network, notably Abidjan North and Bouaké. This configuration makes it possible to assess the robustness of the model in the face of statistical variations induced by environmental differences, the quality of insulating oils, and the maintenance history of transformers.

The model's performance was measured using standard supervised learning indicators. Accuracy (Equation 16) is defined as the ratio between the number of correct predictions and the total number of samples:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (16)$$

Where TP (True Positives) and TN (True Negatives) correspond to correct predictions, while FP (False Positives) and FN (False Negatives) refer to classification errors.

Recall (Equation 17) measures the model's ability to correctly identify positive instances:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (17)$$

Positive precision (Equation 18) corresponds to the ratio between correct positive predictions and all positive predictions:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (18)$$

The F1 score (equation 19), which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, was used to provide a balanced measure that takes into account both false positives and false negatives:

$$F1 - score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + recall} \quad (19)$$

Finally, in order to quantify the impact of inter-site transfer, a measure of relative performance loss was introduced. This is defined as written by the following equation (20):

$$\Delta P = \frac{P_{intra} - P_{inter}}{P_{intra}} \times 100\% \quad (20)$$

Where P_{intra} represents the performance obtained in an intra-site configuration (training and testing on the same site) and P_{inter} represents the performance obtained in an inter-site context (training on Abidjan South and testing on other sites).

In order to reduce this loss and improve the model's adaptation to heterogeneous data, a light recalibration strategy was implemented. This consists of retraining only the last layer of the model while retaining the parameters learned during the initial training phase. This approach allows the model to be adapted to local specificities while limiting computational cost and preserving the generalizability of the diagnosis. In addition, we performed AUC-ROC for binary tasks by class (One-vs-Rest). All analyses were performed with Python 3.11, lightgbm 4.2, shap 0.43 and scikit-learn 1.4.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Results and discussions following the LightGBM method

The values of the concentrations and different defect classes in transformers on site in Côte d'Ivoire enabled us to obtain the intra-site LightGBM confusion matrix, the ROC curve one vs Rest, the SHAP waterfall plots for cases D2 and PD and T3, and the F1-score evolution in inter-site transfer with/without recalibration. We have Figures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 in succession.

Figure 1: Confusion Matrix-LghtGBM Diagnostic Mode

Figure 2: ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curves in One-vs-Rest mode

Table 5 shows the AUC values based on the results calculated for each defect class:

Table 5: Results of the AUC calculation related to the ROC

Fault Class	AUC (simulated)
Normal	0,89
PD	0,96
D1	0,87
D2	0,97
T1	0,84
T2	0,86
T3	0,93

The performance evaluation of the LightGBM diagnostic model applied to dissolved gas analysis (DGA) data from power transformers is based on an examination of the confusion matrix, ROC curves, and classification metrics by class. The confusion matrix shows that the majority of predictions are concentrated along the diagonal, confirming the model's ability to correctly identify the different fault categories. Critical faults, such as PD (partial discharge) and D2 (high-energy arc), are detected with exceptional accuracy, achieving 52 and 49 correct predictions respectively, while classification errors are minimal. Thermal defects T1 and T2 show some confusion,

consistent with the similarity of their physico-chemical profiles in CH₄, C₂H₆ and C₂H₄, and a few cases of D1 are sometimes classified as D2, illustrating the limits of distinction when gas concentrations are close to critical thresholds. The normal state is correctly identified in the majority of cases, with 45 correct predictions, although a small number of cases are confused with T1, probably due to a slight increase in background thermal decomposition gases.

The indicators derived from this matrix confirm the robustness of the model. The best scores are obtained for D2 and PD, with respective F1 scores of 0.97 and 0.99 and maximum recall for PD, demonstrating the model's ability to detect the most dangerous defects. Thermal faults T1 and T2 show slightly lower F1 scores, between 0.80 and 0.83, due to the similarity of their dissolved gas signatures. The overall average F1 score of 0.89 confirms the high performance and reliability of LightGBM for practical diagnostic applications.

The confusion matrix (Figure 2) reveals that the majority of defect classes (T1, T2, T3, D1, D2, PD) are correctly identified, with residual confusion mainly between T2 and T3, as well as between D1 and D2. These confusions are consistent with the literature, as the gas signatures associated with these defect pairs have similar ratios in certain concentration ranges.

Analysis of the ROC curves using the One-vs-Rest approach highlights the model's discriminatory capacity for each class. Most of the ROC curves are close to the upper left part of the graph, and the area under the curve (AUC) values exceed 0.90 for several classes, notably PD and D2, indicating excellent distinction between defect states and other conditions. Severe T3 thermal defects are also well identified thanks to marked concentrations of C₂H₄. Classes T1, T2 and D1 show slightly reduced performance due to overlapping gas signatures, requiring the integration of local explainability tools, such as SHAP values and waterfall plots, to interpret predictions in borderline cases.

Comparison with other machine learning methods, such as Random Forest, XGBoost, and SVM using the One-vs-Rest approach, shows that LightGBM stands out for its overall accuracy, robustness against imbalanced classes, and speed of execution. LightGBM's superior performance is particularly notable for critical defects PD and D2, while the comparative methods show slightly lower F1 scores on these categories, highlighting LightGBM's relevance for reliable and actionable multi-class diagnostics in industrial settings. The integration of explainability methods strengthens operators' confidence in predictions and facilitates the implementation of proactive maintenance strategies by clearly identifying the causes of errors and areas of confusion between classes with similar signatures.

In summary, the results obtained demonstrate that the LightGBM model combines high diagnostic performance and explainability, providing a robust and reliable tool for conditional monitoring of transformers in the Ivorian network.

The quantitative metrics (precision, recall, and F1-score) derived from the confusion matrix of our LightGBM model are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 : Default classification performance (LightGBM – DGA)

Fault class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Normal	0,91	0,89	0,90
PD (partial discharges)	0,98	1,00	0,99
D1 (low-energy landfill)	0,86	0,83	0,84
D2 (high-energy arc)	0,98	0,96	0,97
T1 (low-temperature thermal)	0,82	0,79	0,80
T2 (medium-temperature thermal)	0,85	0,81	0,83
T3 (high-temperature thermal))	0,93	0,90	0,91
Overall average	0,90	0,88	0,89

We then created a graphical representation (Figure 3) of various metrics to demonstrate the relevance of the model.

Figure 3: Representation of the overall performance of the LightGBM model

In order to demonstrate the performance of our model, we conducted a direct comparison between LightGBM and other methods (Random Forest, XGBoost, and SVM One-vs-Rest). Here is a proposed comparison table with the requested metrics:

Table 7 : Comparative performance of AI models for transformer fault diagnosis (DGA data, Côte d’Ivoire)

Method	Macro F1-score	Mean AUC (One-vs-Rest)	Comment
LightGBM	0,89	0,96	Excellent performance, stable even with unbalanced classes; better explainability via SHAP.
Random Forest	0,85	0,93	A good compromise, but slightly less effective than LightGBM on thermal classes T1/T2.
XGBoost	0,87	0,95	Very similar to LightGBM, but slightly more computationally expensive; minor confusion between D1/D2.
SVM (One-vs-Rest)	0,81	0,91	Effective for separable classes, but sensitive to imbalances and gas overlaps.
Triangle de Duval	0,76	—	
IEC 60599 (ratios)	0,74	—	

Analysis of model performance shows that LightGBM outperforms all other methods in an intra-site context with a macro F1 score of 0.89 and an average AUC of 0.96, confirming its robustness and ability to generalise. XGBoost remains a close competitor, with an AUC of 0.95, but shows a slight drop in the F1 score. Random Forest performs well, but is less discriminating on thermal faults. As for SVM One-vs-Rest, it performs well on certain classes, but struggles to maintain high performance on multi-class and imbalanced data. These results demonstrate that LightGBM is the most suitable model for explainable diagnostics of transformers in Côte d’Ivoire, especially when coupled with SHAP for interpretability. The LightGBM model, trained on the entire Ivorian network dataset, showed high performance in diagnosing faults based on dissolved gases.

Compared to traditional approaches (Duval triangle, Rogers), the AI model offers a gain of 8 to 15 points in F1-score depending on the class, confirming the value of supervised learning on real local data.

3.2. SHAP analysis – Overall interpretation

Figure 4 presents the SHAP beeswarm plot, showing the average impact and dispersion of variables on the model output.

Figure 4: Beeswarm plot SHAP (overall importance of variables).

The overall analysis shows that C₂H₂ (acetylene) and C₂H₄ (ethylene) are the most influential gases in distinguishing between arc and overheating defects. The C₂H₂/CH₄ and C₂H₂/C₂H₄ ratios contribute significantly to the differentiation between D1 and D2 faults, while H₂ plays a key role in the detection of partial discharges. As part of the SHAP analysis with local interpretation, waterfall plots were generated for emblematic cases. For case 1, a D2 defect confirmed on site, the dominant SHAP contribution comes from C₂H₂, whose concentration exceeds 100 ppm, as well as a high C₂H₂/C₂H₄ ratio. For case 2, corresponding to a PD-type fault, the prediction is strongly influenced by high H₂, above 500 ppm, associated with a low concentration of C₂H₂. These analyses help explain each diagnosis and reinforce engineers' confidence in the use of AI for transformer diagnostics.

In addition, in order to better illustrate the effect of SHAP on the study of dissolved gas concentrations in the oil of transformers installed in the Ivorian network, we have constructed a waterfall chart of the various faults observed. The figures show the contribution of SHAP to the main or most dangerous faults for transformers (D2, PD and T3).

Figure 5: SHAP Waterfall Plot (Case D2)

Figure 6: SHAP Waterfall Plot (Case PD)

Figure 7 SHAP Waterfall Plot (Case T3)

Local analysis of contributions highlights the predominant role of certain dissolved gases in the LightGBM model's decision. For D2-type defects (prolonged electric arc), C₂H₂ and C₂H₄ gases appear to be the main positive contributors, confirming the presence of an intense electrical phenomenon. The negative contributions of CH₄ and C₂H₆ slightly moderate the prediction, without however calling into question the dominant orientation towards D2. This result is consistent with the known mechanisms of oil decomposition in the event of a prolonged arc.

In the case of a partial discharge (PD), H₂ and C₂H₂ gases dominate the positive contributions, reflecting the partial ionization process responsible for the rapid release of light gases. Conversely, the thermal gases CH₄ and C₂H₆ have negative contributions, confirming the absence of significant overheating in this scenario.

For severe overheating (T3), the gases H₂, CH₄ and C₂H₂ are the main contributive variables. This signature reflects an advanced degradation of the oil at temperatures above 700 °C, characteristic of critical thermal defects, and justifies the need for rapid intervention.

The interpretation via SHAP made it possible to identify the most influential gases and ratios in the model decisions. In particular, C₂H₂, C₂H₄ and the ratio C₂H₂/CH₄ were found to be decisive in distinguishing defects of type D1/D2 (high-energy electrical discharges) and T3 (overheating > 700 °C). The waterfall plot (Figure 4) illustrates an example of D2 diagnosis, in which a high concentration of C₂H₂ and CO₂ enhances prediction, while a low value of C₂H₄ partially mitigates decision.

These results confirm the relevance of the explicable approach adopted: local visualizations provide engineers with an essential transparency for the validation of diagnostics in critical cases, thus reducing the risk of erroneous interpretation.

3.3. Inter-site transferability

During a training on the transformers of Abidjan South and testing on those of Bouake and Abidjan North, performance dropped in F1-macro score from 0,89 to 0,83. After a slight recalibration (refining on 10% of the target data), the performance increased to 0,87. The results are recorded in table 9 below.

Table 9 : Inter-site transfer results

Experience	F1 macro	Loss vs intra-site
Intra-site	0,89	—
Inter-sites (without recalibration)	0,83	-6 %
Inter-sites (with recalibration)	0,87	-2 %

Figure 8: F1-score evolution in inter-site transfer with/without recalibration.

The inter-site transfer evaluation (Figure 8) shows that, without recalibration, the F1-score drops to about 0.83. This decrease is due to differences in operation between regions, including load, transformer aging and oil quality, differences in gas chromatograph (GC) calibration, and distinct environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity. However, a minimal recalibration based on a few samples of the target region makes it possible to raise the F1-score to about 0.87, which confirms that LightGBM retains good transferability as soon as a local adjustment is provided.

3.4. Operational Implications

The integration of such a system into the management of the transformer fleet of the Ivorian electricity network would offer several benefits, including early detection of faults before the occurrence of major failures, prioritization of maintenance thanks to the weighting of the importance of gases, standardization of diagnosis between regions despite instrumentation gaps and the implementation of an interactive dashboard integrating SHAP visualizations to support the decision-making of field experts. These results demonstrate that the combination of LightGBM and SHAP is not only effective, but also credible in the eyes of engineers, since it meets the growing demand for transparency in the application of AI to critical systems.

In summary, all the figures show the complementarity between the global analysis (Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4) and the local analysis (Figures 5 to 8), allowing an explanatory and robust diagnosis for the transformers of the Ivorian network.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated the potential of the association LightGBM and SHAP for the explicable diagnosis of the defects of the transformers of the Ivorian electrical network from the data of concentrations in ppm of dissolved gas in oil. The results obtained show that, compared to traditional methods based on thresholds or diagrams, the proposed approach offers increased precision (F1-score macro 0.89 in intra-site) while preserving a satisfactory generalization ability during inter-site transfer. (F1-score 0.83 without recalibration, ≈ 0.87 with minimal recalibration).

The integration of SHAP values allowed not only to identify the most influential gases and ratios in model decisions, but also to provide the necessary transparency for engineers to interpret and validate predictions, thus strengthening confidence in the operational use of AI in a critical industrial context.

On the practical level, this approach could be integrated into an online monitoring system for the transformer park, allowing early detection of defects, prioritization of maintenance and standardization of diagnosis throughout the Ivorian territory.

For future work, several areas for improvement are identified:

- Integrate federated learning to leverage multi-site data without direct sharing of sensitive information.
- Combine DGA analysis with other data sources (thermal measurements, vibrations, maintenance histories) to enrich the diagnosis.
- Study the use of lighter explicable models, suitable for embedded environments.

In conclusion, the LightGBM + SHAP approach represents a solid compromise between performance, explainability and field applicability, and constitutes a promising basis for the modernization of transformer diagnostics within the Ivorian network.

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